

On certain restricted partition functions

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to establish explicit formulas for certain restricted partition function in terms of divisor function.

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1 Introduction

For any positive integer n , a partition of n is an expression of the form

$$n = n_1 + n_2 + \cdots + n_k$$

with $n_1 \geq n_2 \geq n_3 \geq \cdots \geq n_k$, $k \geq 1$ and the number of partition of n is denoted by $p(n)$. We also define $p(0) = 1$.

P. A. MacMahon calculated $p(n)$ upto 200. Looking the table of $p(n)$ of MacMahon, Ramanujan conjectured that

$$p(5n + 4) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

$$p(7n + 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$$

$$p(11n + 6) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}.$$

Later, all the above conjecture were proved. For details of the above proofs and history one may refer to [7].

Motivated by the above properties of partition function, H. C. Chan [6] studied and extended similar works to the restricted partition function. In fact, he define

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(n)q^n = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^n)(1 - q^{2n})}$$

and proved that $a(3n + 2) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. These are the results motivates many mathematician to work on properties of partition functions. See for example [2],[3],[10].

In this article, our aim is to establish explicit formulas in terms of divisor functions for a restricted partition function $P_{k,a,c}(n)$ defined as follows:

Let $P_{k,a,c}^e(n)$ [or $P_{k,a,c}^o(n)$] denoted the number of partition of n such that

- i . Parts are congruent to $\pm a$ or $\pm c$ or $\frac{k}{2} \pmod{k}$ or $0 \pmod{2k}$.
- ii . Parts are congruent to $\pm a, \frac{k}{2} \pmod{k}$ and $0 \pmod{2k}$ are distinct.
- iii . Parts are congruent to $\frac{k}{2} \pmod{k}$ and $0 \pmod{2k}$ are having two colors.
- iv . Number of parts are congruent to $\frac{k}{2} \pmod{k}$ and $0 \pmod{2k}$ are even(odd).

Let

$$P_{k,a,c}(n) = P_{k,a,c}^e(n) - P_{k,a,c}^o(n).$$

In the next section we prove our main results.

Now we shall recall certain definition which are required to prove our main results. For any complex number a and q with $|q| < 1$,

$$(a; q)_\infty = \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^n).$$

For any integer n , let

$$(a; q)_n = \frac{(a; q)_\infty}{(aq^n; q)_\infty}.$$

Ramanujan's theta function $f(a, b)$ is defined by

$$f(a, b) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}} b^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}, \quad |ab| < 1.$$

From the well known Jacobi's triple product identity, we have

$$f(a, b) = (-a; ab)_\infty (-b; ab)_\infty (ab; ab)_\infty.$$

A special case of $f(a, b)$, $\psi(q)$ is defined by

$$\psi(q) := f(q, q^3) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}} = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty}{(q; q^2)_\infty}.$$

By the above definition of $f(a, b)$ and $\psi(q)$, one can easily see that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_{k,a,c}(n)q^n = \psi^2(-q^k) \frac{f(q^a, q^b)}{f(-q^c, -q^d)}, \quad \text{where } a + b = c + d = 2k. \quad (1.1)$$

Let $d_{x,y}(n)$ denotes the number of divisor of n which are congruent to $x \pmod{y}$ if n is a positive integer and $d_{x,y}(n) = 0$ otherwise.

2 Main results

In this section, we establish explicit formulas in terms of divisor functions for a restricted partition function $P_{k,a,c}(n)$.

Lemma 2.1. *For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have*

$$\psi^2(q^2) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} t_2(n)q^n$$

and

$$t_2(n) = d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1),$$

where $t_2(n)$ is the number of representation of an integer n as a sum of two triangular number.

For a proof of above lemma, one may refer to [1].

Theorem 2.2. *The following identity holds:*

$$P_{6,2,1}(n) = d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{3}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{3}\right).$$

Proof. From [4], we have

$$\psi^2(-q^3) \frac{f(q^2, q^4)}{f(-q, -q^5)} = \psi^2(q^2) + q\psi^2(q^6).$$

Employing (1.1) and Lemma 2.1 in the above, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_{6,2,1}(n)q^n \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{3}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{3}\right) \right\} q^n. \end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficient of q^n in the above equation, we obtain the required result. $\square$

Example: For $n = 8$, we have

$P_{6,2,1}^e(8)$	$P_{6,2,1}^o(8)$	$P_{6,2,1}(8)$
8, 7+1, 5+2+1 5+1+1+1 4+2+1+1, 4+1+1+1+1, 2+1+1+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1+1+1, $3_r + 3_g + 1 + 1$, $3_r + 3_g + 2$.	$5 + 3_r$, $5 + 3_g$, $4 + 3_r + 1$, $4 + 3_g + 1$, $3_r + 2 + 1 + 1 + 1$, $3_g + 2 + 1 + 1 + 1$, $3_r + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$, $3_g + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$.	②

(Table-1)

One can easily see that

$$d_{1,4}(17) = 2, d_{3,4}(17) = 0, d_{1,4}\left(\frac{17}{3}\right) = 0 \text{ and } d_{3,4}\left(\frac{17}{3}\right) = 0.$$

From Table-1 and the above, we have

$$P_{6,2,1}(8) = d_{1,4}(17) - d_{3,4}(17) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{17}{3}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{17}{3}\right) = 2.$$

This verifies the theorem for $n = 8$.

Theorem 2.3. *The following identity holds:*

$$P_{10,4,1}(n) - P_{10,2,3}(n-1) = d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) - d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{5}\right) + d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{5}\right).$$

Proof. From [5, p. 263], we have

$$\psi^2(q^5) \left[\frac{f(q^4, q^6)}{f(q, q^9)} + q \frac{f(q^2, q^8)}{f(q^3, q^7)} \right] = \psi^2(q^2) - q^2 \psi^2(q^{10}).$$

By changing q to $-q$ in the above equation, we have

$$\psi^2(-q^5) \left[\frac{f(q^4, q^6)}{f(-q, -q^9)} - q \frac{f(q^2, q^8)}{f(-q^3, -q^7)} \right] = \psi^2(q^2) - q^2 \psi^2(q^{10}).$$

Employing (1.1) and Lemma 2.1 in the above, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{P_{10,4,1}(n) - P_{10,2,3}(n-1)\} q^n \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) - d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{5}\right) + d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{5}\right) \right\} q^n. \end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficient of q^n in the above equation, we obtain the required result. $\square$

Example: For $n = 10$, we have

$P_{10,4,1}^e(10)$	$P_{10,4,1}^o(10)$	$P_{10,4,1}(10)$
$1+9,$ $4+6,$ $1+1+1+1+6,$ $1+1+1+1+1+4,$ $1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1,$ $5_r + 5_g$	$1+1+1+1+1+5_r,$ $1+1+1+1+1+5_g,$ $1+4+5_r,$ $1+4+5_g.$	②

(Table-2)

$P_{10,2,3}^e(9)$	$P_{10,2,3}^o(9)$	$P_{10,2,3}(9)$
$3+3+3,$ $2+7.$	–	②

(Table-3)

One can easily see that

$$d_{1,4}(21) = 2, d_{3,4}(21) = 2, d_{1,4}\left(\frac{21}{5}\right) = 0 \text{ and } d_{3,4}\left(\frac{21}{5}\right) = 0.$$

From Table-2,3 and the above, we have

$$P_{10,4,1}(10) - P_{10,2,3}(9) = d_{1,4}(21) - d_{3,4}(21) - d_{1,4}\left(\frac{21}{5}\right) + d_{3,4}\left(\frac{21}{5}\right) = 0.$$

This verifies the theorem for $n = 10$.

Theorem 2.4. *The following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P_{14,6,1}(n) - P_{14,4,3}(n-1) + P_{14,2,5}(n-2) \\
 &= d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{7}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{7}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From [11], we have

$$\psi^2(q^7) \left[\frac{f(q^6, q^8)}{f(q, q^{13})} + q \frac{f(q^4, q^{10})}{f(q^3, q^{11})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^2, q^{12})}{f(q^5, q^9)} \right] = \psi^2(q^2) - q^3 \psi^2(q^{14}).$$

By changing q to $-q$ in the above equation, we have

$$\psi^2(-q^7) \left[\frac{f(q^6, q^8)}{f(-q, -q^{13})} - q \frac{f(q^4, q^{10})}{f(-q^3, -q^{11})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^2, q^{12})}{f(-q^5, -q^9)} \right] = \psi^2(q^2) + q^3 \psi^2(q^{14}).$$

Employing (1.1) and Lemma 2.1 in the above, we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{P_{14,6,1}(n) - P_{14,4,3}(n-1) + P_{14,2,5}(n-2)\} q^n$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{7}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{7}\right) \right\} q^n.$$

By comparing the coefficient of q^n in the above equation, we obtain the required result. □

Example: For $n = 12$, we have

$P_{14,6,1}^e(12)$	$P_{14,6,1}^o(12)$	$P_{14,6,1}(12)$
1+1+1+1+8, 1+1+1+1+1+1+6, 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1.	1+1+1+1+1+7 _r , 1+1+1+1+1+7 _g .	①

(Table-4)

$P_{14,4,3}^e(11)$	$P_{14,4,3}^o(11)$	$P_{14,4,3}(11)$
11	4+7 _r 4+7 _g	①-1

(Table-5)

$P_{14,2,5}^e(10)$	$P_{14,2,5}^o(10)$	$P_{14,2,5}(10)$
5+5	-	①

(Table-6)

One can easily see that

$$d_{1,4}(25) = 3, d_{3,4}(25) = 0, d_{1,4}\left(\frac{25}{7}\right) = 0 \text{ and } d_{3,4}\left(\frac{25}{7}\right) = 0.$$

From Table-4,3,6 and the above, we have

$$P_{14,6,1}(12) - P_{14,4,3}(11) + P_{14,2,5}(10) = d_{1,4}(25) - d_{3,4}(25) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{25}{7}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{25}{7}\right) = 3.$$

This verifies the theorem for $n = 12$.

Theorem 2.5. *The following identity holds:*

$$\psi^2(q^2) - q^4 \psi^2(q^{18}) = \psi^2(q^9) \left[\frac{f(q^8, q^{10})}{f(q, q^{17})} + q \frac{f(q^6, q^{12})}{f(q^3, q^{15})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^4, q^{14})}{f(q^5, q^{13})} + q^3 \frac{f(q^2, q^{16})}{f(q^7, q^{11})} \right].$$

Proof. In [9, p. 216], Ramanujan recorded following identity:

$$\psi^2(q^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^k}{1 + q^{2k+1}}.$$

Which implies

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^2(q^2) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k}}{1 + q^{18k+1}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+1}}{1 + q^{18k+3}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+2}}{1 + q^{18k+5}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+3}}{1 + q^{18k+7}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+4}}{1 + q^{18k+9}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+5}}{1 + q^{18k+11}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+6}}{1 + q^{18k+13}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+7}}{1 + q^{18k+15}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+8}}{1 + q^{18k+17}}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^2(q^2) - q^4\psi^2(q^{18}) &= \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k}}{1 + q^{18k+1}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+1}}{1 + q^{18k+3}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+2}}{1 + q^{18k+5}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k+3}}{1 + q^{18k+7}}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

The following is the famous Ramanujan's ${}_1\psi_1$ summation formula [5, p. 34]:

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(a; q)_k}{(b; q)_k} z^k = \frac{(az; q)_{\infty} (q/az; q)_{\infty} (q; q)_{\infty} (b/a; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty} (b/az; q)_{\infty} (b; q)_{\infty} (q/a; q)_{\infty}}, \quad |b/a| < |z| < 1. \tag{2.2}$$

Setting $b = aq$ and $z = q^9$ in the above equation and then replacing q by q^{18} , we obtain

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k}}{1 - aq^{18k}} = \frac{f(-aq^9, -q^9/a)(q^{18}; q^{18})_{\infty}^3}{f(-q^9, -q^9)f(-a, -q^{18}/a)}. \tag{2.3}$$

Which implies

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{9k}}{1 - aq^{18k}} = \psi^2(q^9) \frac{f(-aq^9, -q^9/a)}{f(-a, -q^{18}/a)}. \tag{2.4}$$

Employing (2.4) in (2.1) with $a = -q, -q^3, -q^5$, and $-q^7$, we obtain the required result. $\square$

Theorem 2.6. *The following identity holds:*

$$P_{18,8,1}(n) - P_{18,6,3}(n - 1) + P_{18,4,5}(n - 2) - P_{18,2,7}(n - 3) \\ = d_{1,4}(2n + 1) - d_{3,4}(2n + 1) - d_{1,4} \left(\frac{2n + 1}{9} \right) + d_{3,4} \left(\frac{2n + 1}{9} \right).$$

Proof. From previous theorem, we have

$$\left[\frac{f(q^8, q^{10})}{f(q, q^{17})} + q \frac{f(q^6, q^{12})}{f(q^3, q^{15})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^4, q^{14})}{f(q^5, q^{13})} + q^3 \frac{f(q^2, q^{16})}{f(q^7, q^{11})} \right] \psi^2(q^9) = \psi^2(q^2) - q^4 \psi^2(q^{18}).$$

Changing q to $-q$ in the above equation, we have

$$\left[\frac{f(q^8, q^{10})}{f(-q, -q^{17})} - q \frac{f(q^6, q^{12})}{f(-q^3, -q^{15})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^4, q^{14})}{f(-q^5, -q^{13})} - q^3 \frac{f(q^2, q^{16})}{f(-q^7, -q^{11})} \right] \psi^2(-q^9) \\ = \psi^2(q^2) - q^4 \psi^2(q^{18}).$$

Employing (1.1) and Lemma 2.1 in the above, we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{P_{18,8,1}(n) - P_{18,6,3}(n - 1) + P_{18,4,5}(n - 2) - P_{18,2,7}(n - 3)\} q^n \\ = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ d_{1,4}(2n + 1) - d_{3,4}(2n + 1) - d_{1,4} \left(\frac{2n + 1}{9} \right) + d_{3,4} \left(\frac{2n + 1}{9} \right) \right\} q^n.$$

By comparing the coefficient of q^n in the above equation, we obtain the required result. □

Example: For $n = 14$, we have

$P_{18,8,1}^e(14)$	$P_{18,8,1}^o(14)$	$P_{18,8,1}(14)$
1+1+1+1+10, 1+1+1+1+1+8, 1+1+1+1+1+1+1 +1+1+1+1+1+1.	1+1+1+1+1+9 _r , 1+1+1+1+1+9 _g ,	①

(Table-7)

$P_{18,6,3}^e(13)$	$P_{18,6,3}^o(13)$	$P_{18,6,3}(13)$
-	-	①

(Table-8)

$P_{18,4,5}^e(12)$	$P_{18,4,5}^o(12)$	$P_{18,4,5}(12)$
–	–	0

(Table-9)

$P_{18,2,7}^e(11)$	$P_{18,2,7}^o(11)$	$P_{18,2,7}(11)$
11	$2 + 9_r,$ $2 + 9_g.$	-1

(Table-10)

One can easily see that

$$d_{1,4}(29) = 2, d_{3,4}(29) = 0, d_{1,4}\left(\frac{29}{9}\right) = 0 \text{ and } d_{3,4}\left(\frac{29}{9}\right) = 0.$$

From Table-7,8,9,10 and the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{18,8,1}(14) - P_{18,6,3}(13) + P_{18,4,5}(12) - P_{18,2,7}(11) \\ = d_{1,4}(29) - d_{3,4}(29) - d_{1,4}\left(\frac{29}{9}\right) + d_{3,4}\left(\frac{29}{9}\right) = 2. \end{aligned}$$

This verifies the theorem for $n = 14$.

Theorem 2.7. *The following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} P_{22,10,1}(n) - P_{22,8,3}(n-1) + P_{22,6,5}(n-2) - P_{22,4,7}(n-3) + P_{22,2,9}(n-4) \\ = d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{11}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{11}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From [8], we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{f(q^{10}, q^{12})}{f(q, q^{21})} + q \frac{f(q^8, q^{14})}{f(q^3, q^{19})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^6, q^{16})}{f(q^5, q^{17})} + q^3 \frac{f(q^4, q^{18})}{f(q^7, q^{15})} + q^4 \frac{f(q^2, q^{20})}{f(q^9, q^{13})} \right] \psi^2(q^{11}) \\ = \psi^2(q^2) - q^5 \psi^2(q^{22}). \end{aligned}$$

By changing q to $-q$ in the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{f(q^{10}, q^{12})}{f(-q, -q^{21})} - q \frac{f(q^8, q^{14})}{f(-q^3, -q^{19})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^6, q^{16})}{f(-q^5, -q^{17})} - q^3 \frac{f(q^4, q^{18})}{f(-q^7, -q^{15})} + q^4 \frac{f(q^2, q^{20})}{f(-q^9, -q^{13})} \right] \\ \times \psi^2(-q^{11}) = \psi^2(q^2) + q^5 \psi^2(q^{22}). \end{aligned}$$

Employing (1.1) and Lemma 2.1 in the above, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{P_{22,10,1}(n) - P_{22,8,3}(n-1) + P_{22,6,5}(n-2) - P_{22,4,7}(n-3) + P_{22,2,9}(n-4)\} q^n \\ = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{11}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{11}\right) \right\} q^n. \end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficient of q^n in the above equation, we obtain the required result. □

Example: For $n = 16$, we have

$P_{22,10,1}^e(16)$	$P_{22,10,1}^o(16)$	$P_{22,10,1}(16)$
12+1+1+1+1+1, 10+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1.	11 _r +1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1 , 11 _g +1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1,	①

(Table-11)

$P_{22,8,3}^e(15)$	$P_{22,8,3}^o(15)$	$P_{22,8,3}(15)$
3+3+3+3	—	①

(Table-12)

$P_{22,6,5}^e(14)$	$P_{22,6,5}^o(14)$	$P_{22,6,5}(14)$
—	—	①

(Table-13)

$P_{22,4,7}^e(13)$	$P_{22,4,7}^o(13)$	$P_{22,4,7}(13)$
—	—	①

(Table-14)

$P_{22,2,9}^e(12)$	$P_{22,2,9}^o(12)$	$P_{22,2,9}(12)$
—	—	①

(Table-15)

One can easily see that

$$d_{1,4}(33) = 2, d_{3,4}(33) = 2, d_{1,4}\left(\frac{33}{11}\right) = 1 \text{ and } d_{3,4}\left(\frac{33}{11}\right) = 1.$$

From Table-11,12,13,14,15 and the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{22,10,1}(16) - P_{22,8,3}(15) + P_{22,6,5}(14) - P_{22,4,7}(13) + P_{22,2,9}(12) \\ = d_{1,4}(33) - d_{3,4}(33) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{33}{11}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{33}{11}\right) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

This verifies the theorem for $n = 16$.

Theorem 2.8. *The following identity holds:*

$$\psi^2(q^2) - q^6\psi^2(q^{26}) = \psi^2(q^{13}) \times \left[\frac{f(q^{12}, q^{14})}{f(q, q^{25})} + q \frac{f(q^{10}, q^{16})}{f(q^3, q^{23})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^8, q^{18})}{f(q^5, q^{21})} + q^3 \frac{f(q^6, q^{20})}{f(q^7, q^{19})} + q^4 \frac{f(q^4, q^{22})}{f(q^9, q^{17})} + q^5 \frac{f(q^2, q^{24})}{f(q^{11}, q^{15})} \right].$$

Proof. In [9, p. 216], Ramanujan recorded following identity:

$$\psi^2(q^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^k}{1 + q^{2k+1}}.$$

Which implies

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^2(q^2) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k}}{1 + q^{26k+1}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+1}}{1 + q^{26k+3}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+2}}{1 + q^{26k+5}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+3}}{1 + q^{26k+7}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+4}}{1 + q^{26k+9}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+5}}{1 + q^{26k+11}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+6}}{1 + q^{26k+13}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+7}}{1 + q^{26k+15}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+8}}{1 + q^{26k+17}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+9}}{1 + q^{26k+19}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+10}}{1 + q^{26k+21}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+11}}{1 + q^{26k+23}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+12}}{1 + q^{26k+25}}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^2(q^2) - q^6\psi^2(q^{26}) &= \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k}}{1 + q^{26k+1}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+1}}{1 + q^{26k+3}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+2}}{1 + q^{26k+5}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+3}}{1 + q^{26k+7}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+4}}{1 + q^{26k+9}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k+5}}{1 + q^{26k+11}} \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

Setting $b = aq$ and $z = q^{13}$ in the Ramanujan's ${}_1\psi_1$ summation formula (2.2) and then replacing q by q^{26} , we obtain

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k}}{1 - aq^{26k}} = \frac{f(-aq^{13}, -q^{13}/a)(q^{26}; q^{26})_{\infty}^3}{f(-q^{13}, -q^{13})f(-a, -q^{26}/a)}. \tag{2.6}$$

Which implies

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{13k}}{1 - aq^{26k}} = \psi^2(q^{13}) \frac{f(-aq^{13}, -q^{13}/a)}{f(-a, -q^{26}/a)}. \tag{2.7}$$

Employing (2.7) in (2.5) with $a = -q, -q^3, -q^5, -q^7, -q^9$, and $-q^{11}$, we obtain the required result. $\square$

Theorem 2.9. *The following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P_{26,12,1}(n) - P_{26,10,3}(n-1) + P_{26,8,5}(n-2) \\
 &\quad - P_{26,6,7}(n-3) + P_{26,4,9}(n-4) - P_{26,2,11}(n-5) \\
 &= d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) - d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{13}\right) + d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{13}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From previous theorem, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{f(q^{12}, q^{14})}{f(q, q^{25})} + q \frac{f(q^{10}, q^{16})}{f(q^3, q^{23})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^8, q^{18})}{f(q^5, q^{21})} + q^3 \frac{f(q^6, q^{20})}{f(q^7, q^{19})} + q^4 \frac{f(q^4, q^{22})}{f(q^9, q^{17})} + q^5 \frac{f(q^2, q^{24})}{f(q^{11}, q^{15})} \right] \\
 &\quad \times \psi^2(q^{13}) = \psi^2(q^2) - q^4 \psi^2(q^{26})
 \end{aligned}$$

Changing q to $-q$ in the above equation, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{f(q^{12}, q^{14})}{f(-q, -q^{25})} - q \frac{f(q^{10}, q^{16})}{f(-q^3, -q^{23})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^8, q^{18})}{f(-q^5, -q^{21})} - q^3 \frac{f(q^6, q^{20})}{f(-q^7, -q^{19})} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + q^4 \frac{f(q^4, q^{22})}{f(-q^9, -q^{17})} - q^5 \frac{f(q^2, q^{24})}{f(-q^{11}, -q^{15})} \right] \psi^2(-q^{13}) \\
 &= \psi^2(q^2) - q^4 \psi^2(q^{26}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Employing (1.1) and Lemma 2.1 in the above, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ P_{26,12,1}(n) - P_{26,10,3}(n-1) + P_{26,8,5}(n-2) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - P_{26,6,7}(n-3) + P_{26,4,9}(n-4) - P_{26,2,11}(n-5) \right\} q^n \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) - d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{13}\right) + d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{13}\right) \right\} q^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficient of q^n in the above equation, we obtain the required result. $\square$

Example: For $n = 18$, we have

$P_{26,12,1}^e(18)$	$P_{26,12,1}^o(18)$	$P_{26,12,1}(18)$
12+1+1+1+1+1+1, 14+1+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1 +1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1.	13 _r +1+1+1+1+1, 13 _g +1+1+1+1+1.	①

(Table-16)

$P_{26,10,3}^e(17)$	$P_{26,10,3}^o(17)$	$P_{26,10,3}(17)$
–	–	0

(Table-17)

$P_{26,8,5}^e(16)$	$P_{26,8,5}^o(16)$	$P_{26,8,5}(16)$
–	–	0

(Table-18)

$P_{26,6,7}^e(15)$	$P_{26,6,7}^o(15)$	$P_{26,6,7}(15)$
–	–	0

(Table-19)

$P_{26,4,9}^e(14)$	$P_{26,4,9}^o(14)$	$P_{26,4,9}(14)$
–	–	0

(Table-20)

$P_{26,2,11}^e(13)$	$P_{26,2,11}^o(13)$	$P_{26,2,11}(13)$
2+11	13_r 13_g	-1

(Table-21)

One can easily see that

$$d_{1,4}(37) = 2, d_{3,4}(37) = 0, d_{1,4}\left(\frac{37}{13}\right) = 0 \text{ and } d_{3,4}\left(\frac{37}{13}\right) = 0.$$

From Table-16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21 and the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &P_{26,12,1}(18) - P_{26,10,3}(17) + P_{26,8,5}(16) \\ &\quad - P_{26,6,7}(15) + P_{26,4,9}(14) - P_{26,2,11}(13) \\ &= d_{1,4}(37) - d_{3,4}(37) - d_{1,4}\left(\frac{37}{13}\right) + d_{3,4}\left(\frac{37}{13}\right) = 2. \end{aligned}$$

This verifies the theorem for $n = 18$.

Theorem 2.10. *The following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} &\psi^2(q^2) - q^7\psi^2(q^{30}) \\ &= \psi^2(q^{15}) \left[\frac{f(q^{14}, q^{16})}{f(q, q^{29})} + q \frac{f(q^{12}, q^{18})}{f(q^3, q^{27})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^{10}, q^{20})}{f(q^5, q^{25})} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + q^3 \frac{f(q^8, q^{22})}{f(q^7, q^{23})} + q^4 \frac{f(q^6, q^{24})}{f(q^9, q^{21})} + q^5 \frac{f(q^4, q^{26})}{f(q^{11}, q^{19})} + q^6 \frac{f(q^2, q^{28})}{f(q^{13}, q^{17})} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. In [9, p. 216], Ramanujan recorded following identity:

$$\psi^2(q^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^k}{1 + q^{2k+1}}.$$

Which implies

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^2(q^2) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k}}{1 + q^{30k+1}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+1}}{1 + q^{30k+3}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+2}}{1 + q^{30k+5}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+3}}{1 + q^{30k+7}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+4}}{1 + q^{30k+9}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+5}}{1 + q^{30k+11}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+6}}{1 + q^{30k+13}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+7}}{1 + q^{30k+15}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+8}}{1 + q^{30k+17}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+9}}{1 + q^{30k+19}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+10}}{1 + q^{30k+21}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+11}}{1 + q^{30k+23}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+12}}{1 + q^{30k+25}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+13}}{1 + q^{30k+27}} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+14}}{1 + q^{30k+29}}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^2(q^2) - q^7\psi^2(q^{30}) &= \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k}}{1 + q^{30k+1}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+1}}{1 + q^{30k+3}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+2}}{1 + q^{30k+5}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+3}}{1 + q^{30k+7}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+4}}{1 + q^{30k+9}} + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+5}}{1 + q^{30k+11}} \\ &+ \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k+6}}{1 + q^{30k+13}}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

Setting $b = aq$ and $z = q^{15}$ in the Ramanujan's ${}_1\psi_1$ summation formula (2.2) and then replacing q by q^{30} , we obtain

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k}}{1 - aq^{30k}} = \frac{f(-aq^{15}, -q^{15}/a)(q^{30}, q^{30})_{\infty}^3}{f(-q^{15}, -q^{15})f(-a, -q^{30}/a)}. \tag{2.9}$$

Which implies

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{q^{15k}}{1 - aq^{30k}} = \psi^2(q^{15}) \frac{f(-aq^{15}, -q^{15}/a)}{f(-a, -q^{30}/a)}. \tag{2.10}$$

Employing (2.10) in (2.8) with $a = -q, -q^3, -q^5, -q^7, -q^9, -q^{11}$ and $-q^{13}$, we obtain the required result. □

Theorem 2.11. *The following identity holds:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P_{30,14,1}(n) - P_{30,12,3}(n-1) + P_{30,10,5}(n-2) \\
 &\quad - P_{30,8,7}(n-3) + P_{30,6,9}(n-4) - P_{30,4,11}(n-5) + P_{30,2,13}(n-6) \\
 &\quad = d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{15}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{15}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From previous theorem, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{f(q^{14}, q^{16})}{f(q, q^{29})} + q \frac{f(q^{12}, q^{18})}{f(q^3, q^{27})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^{10}, q^{20})}{f(q^5, q^{25})} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + q^3 \frac{f(q^8, q^{22})}{f(q^7, q^{23})} + q^4 \frac{f(q^6, q^{24})}{f(q^9, q^{21})} + q^5 \frac{f(q^4, q^{26})}{f(q^{11}, q^{19})} + q^6 \frac{f(q^2, q^{28})}{f(q^{13}, q^{17})} \right] \psi^2(q^{15}) \\
 &\quad = \psi^2(q^2) - q^7 \psi^2(q^{30})
 \end{aligned}$$

By changing q to $-q$ in the above equation, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{f(q^{14}, q^{16})}{f(-q, -q^{29})} + q \frac{f(q^{12}, q^{18})}{f(-q^3, -q^{27})} + q^2 \frac{f(q^{10}, q^{20})}{f(-q^5, -q^{25})} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - q^3 \frac{f(q^8, q^{22})}{f(-q^7, -q^{23})} + q^4 \frac{f(q^6, q^{24})}{f(-q^9, -q^{21})} - q^5 \frac{f(q^4, q^{26})}{f(-q^{11}, -q^{19})} + q^6 \frac{f(q^2, q^{28})}{f(-q^{13}, -q^{17})} \right] \\
 &\quad \times \psi^2(-q^{15}) = \psi^2(q^2) + q^7 \psi^2(q^{30})
 \end{aligned}$$

Employing (1.1) and Lemma 2.1 in the above, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ P_{30,14,1}(n) - P_{30,12,3}(n-1) + P_{30,10,5}(n-2) - P_{30,8,7}(n-3) + P_{30,6,9}(n-4) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - P_{30,4,11}(n-5) + P_{30,2,13}(n-6) \right\} q^n \\
 &\quad = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\{ d_{1,4}(2n+1) - d_{3,4}(2n+1) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{15}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{2n+1}{15}\right) \right\} q^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficient of q^n in the above equation, we obtain the required result. $\square$

Example: For $n = 20$, we have

$P_{30,14,1}^e(20)$	$P_{30,14,1}^o(20)$	$P_{30,14,1}(20)$
16+1+1+1+1+1, 14+1+1+1+1+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1 +1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1 .	15 _r +1+1+1+1+1+1+1 15 _g +1+1+1+1+1+1+1	①

(Table-22)

$P_{30,12,3}^e(19)$	$P_{30,12,3}^o(19)$	$P_{30,12,3}(19)$
–	–	0

(Table-23)

$P_{30,10,5}^e(18)$	$P_{30,10,5}^o(18)$	$P_{30,10,5}(18)$
–	–	0

(Table-24)

$P_{30,8,7}^e(17)$	$P_{30,8,7}^o(17)$	$P_{30,8,7}(17)$
–	–	0

(Table-25)

$P_{30,6,9}^e(16)$	$P_{30,6,9}^o(16)$	$P_{30,6,9}(16)$
–	–	0

(Table-26)

$P_{30,4,11}^e(15)$	$P_{30,4,9}^o(15)$	$P_{30,4,9}(11)$
4+11	15_r , 15_g .	-1

(Table-27)

$P_{30,2,13}^e(14)$	$P_{30,2,13}^o(14)$	$P_{30,2,13}(14)$
–	–	0

(Table-28)

One can easily see that

$$d_{1,4}(41) = 2, d_{3,4}(41) = 0, d_{1,4}\left(\frac{41}{15}\right) = 0 \text{ and } d_{3,4}\left(\frac{41}{15}\right) = 0.$$

From Table-22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28 and the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &P_{30,14,1}(20) - P_{30,12,3}(19) + P_{30,10,5}(18) - P_{30,8,7}(17) \\ &\quad + P_{30,6,9}(16) - P_{30,4,11}(15) + P_{30,2,13}(14) \\ &= d_{1,4}(41) - d_{3,4}(41) + d_{1,4}\left(\frac{41}{15}\right) - d_{3,4}\left(\frac{41}{15}\right) = 2. \end{aligned}$$

This verifies the theorem for $n = 20$.

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